

Research Article

Innovating Financial Literacy through Immersive Experience: A Preliminary Study

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Abstract: Financial literacy is increasingly recognized as an essential skill for both personal empowerment and societal advancement. In the context of education, equipping students with the financial knowledge necessary for long-term success is critical. This preliminary study explores the potential of immersive learning technologies, particularly virtual reality (VR), in enhancing financial literacy among young adults aged 18 to 35. The study utilizes a qualitative approach, employing open-ended questionnaires to gather insights into participants' financial attitudes, literacy, and educational needs. The findings reveal that early financial experiences significantly shape participants' current financial attitudes, with a strong emphasis on saving and disciplined money management. However, a critical gap in formal financial education is apparent, with most participants reporting that they had not received structured financial instruction during their education. Despite this, participants demonstrated a keen understanding of the importance of financial literacy in areas such as budgeting, saving, and investment. A notable outcome of the study is the preference for immersive and engaging learning methods. The majority of participants expressed a desire for gamified learning experiences or VR-based financial education, viewing these methods as more engaging and effective than traditional classroom approaches. This preference underscores the potential for innovative, technology-driven financial literacy programs to bridge the existing education gap. The study contributes to Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), particularly Target 4.4, which focuses on equipping individuals with relevant skills for employment and economic stability.

Keywords: financial literacy; virtual reality (VR); immersive learning; financial education; qualitative research; gamification; higher education; financial attitudes

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1. INTRODUCTION

Financial literacy, encompassing essential skills such as budgeting, saving, investing, and debt management, is recognized as a crucial life competency that significantly impacts both personal and societal well-being. In an increasingly complex financial world, individuals are required to make informed decisions that affect their long-term economic stability. Despite the growing importance of financial literacy, many university students, particularly those from low-income backgrounds, face barriers to acquiring these critical skills. These barriers are often due to the lack of engaging and

effective educational resources, which leaves students inadequately prepared to manage their finances in real-world situations (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014).

Lusardi and Mitchell (2014) define financial literacy as the ability to process economic information and make informed decisions about financial planning, wealth accumulation, debt, and retirement. Their research underscores that financial literacy is not merely an academic skill but a key determinant of an individual's financial well-being and overall economic stability. The increasing complexity of financial management, driven by globalization and financial market liberalization, has shifted the onus of financial well-being onto individuals (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2017). This necessitates a heightened emphasis on financial literacy and responsible financial conduct (She et al., 2024). Research underscores the significance of numerical comprehension and a positive emotional disposition towards finances as pivotal components of financial capability (Strömbäck et al., 2020). Studies demonstrate that individuals with a stronger grasp of financial concepts and responsible financial habits are more adept at managing their finances, including credit card usage, bill payments, budgeting, and overall financial decision-making (Hamid & Loke, 2021). Young adults, in particular, face financial challenges, with rising levels of debt from student loans, credit cards, and other forms of credit. For instance, in the United States alone, student loan debt reached a staggering \$1.73 trillion as of Q1 2023 (Education Data, 2023), highlighting the scale of the problem. Similar trends are observed in other countries such as the United Kingdom and Australia, where youth debt is steadily increasing (Financial Literacy and Education Commission, 2020).

In Malaysia, financial challenges among youth are also significant, with 73% of individuals aged 18-40 reportedly in debt, struggling to meet financial commitments (Says, 2023). Low financial literacy levels among young adults have been directly linked to adverse financial outcomes, including higher debt levels, lower credit scores, and increased financial stress (OECD, 2016). These financial struggles underscore the importance of providing effective financial education to young adults, equipping them with the necessary skills to navigate increasingly complex financial systems. highlights a concerning trend in Malaysia: a significant number of young people are burdened by debt, coupled with a low level of financial literacy. The Credit Counselling and Debt Management Agency (AKPK) reports that over 53,000 individuals under 30 owe nearly RM1.9 billion in debt. Meanwhile, the OECD financial literacy survey found that only 36% of Malaysians understand basic financial concepts. This lack of financial knowledge is particularly worrying given Malaysia's high household debt, which reached 84.2% of GDP in 2023 (Bernama, 2024). The text emphasizes the importance of financial literacy in preventing long-term financial strain. Studies by Yaakob and Dahalan (2019) suggest that low financial literacy is correlated with heightened financial stress and reduced financial satisfaction among young adults. Similarly, Kassim et al. (2021) found that university students with higher financial literacy were more likely to engage in positive financial behaviors, such as paying bills on time and maintaining a good credit score. These findings indicate that improving financial literacy can lead to better financial outcomes, making it a critical area for educational intervention.

In higher education, research has consistently shown that students generally have low levels of financial literacy, which can result in poor financial decisions with long-term consequences. For example, Chen and Volpe (1998) revealed that college students' lack of financial knowledge often led to suboptimal financial behavior. More recent research by Friedline and West (2016) confirms that these issues persist, highlighting the urgent need for more effective financial education interventions in university settings. These interventions must go beyond traditional teaching methods and incorporate active, engaging learning techniques that cater to the needs of young adults.

A growing body of literature supports the use of immersive learning technologies, such as game-based learning and virtual reality (VR), to improve financial literacy. Studies by Merchant et al. (2014) and Carlin et al. (2017) show that interactive learning experiences can significantly enhance financial literacy and promote better financial decision-making. Deng et al. (2019) found that VR-based learning environments not only improved financial knowledge but also increased student engagement, suggesting that immersive technologies can be an effective tool in financial education.

Given these challenges and the potential of innovative learning technologies, this study explores the role of immersive learning in enhancing financial literacy among young adults. The aim is to develop immersive learning tools that can be integrated into higher education curricula, helping students acquire the financial skills needed for financial independence and success. By addressing Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), specifically Target 4.4, this study contributes to efforts aimed at equipping individuals with relevant skills for employment and sustainable development.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research design aimed at exploring the financial literacy experiences and attitudes of young adults. The research utilizes open-ended questionnaires distributed to a focus group to capture in-depth insights into participants' thoughts and experiences. Given that the research is preliminary in nature, this qualitative approach was chosen to facilitate an exploratory investigation that can inform future quantitative research.

The primary method of data collection involved a structured open-ended questionnaire administered through Google Forms. This allowed participants to freely express their perspectives without being constrained by predefined answer categories. The questionnaire design was carefully structured to cover various aspects of financial experiences, behaviors, and attitudes, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of each participant's financial literacy.

2.2 Participant Selection

The study involved six participants, all young adults aged between 18 and 35 years. These participants were invited to participate in the survey based on their willingness and availability. The focus group composition was diverse, though no specific subgroups were emphasized in the analysis. The goal was to gather broad insights into the financial experiences and literacy levels of young adults without focusing on occupational or educational distinctions.

2.3 Data Collection

The questionnaire distributed to participants consisted of 53 open-ended questions that were categorized into various themes:

- **Demographic Information:** 3 questions aimed at gathering basic information such as age, gender, and educational background.
- **Financial Background and Early Experiences:** 6 questions that explored participants' early exposure to financial concepts and their upbringing in relation to money.

- **Current Financial Situation and Behaviors:** 7 questions that investigated participants' current financial practices, such as budgeting, saving, and spending habits.
- **Financial Knowledge and Learning:** 8 questions focusing on how participants acquired financial knowledge, either through formal education or personal experiences.
- **Financial Challenges and Opportunities:** 7 questions that delved into the obstacles participants face in managing their finances and any perceived opportunities for improving their financial health.
- **Investment and Risk Attitudes:** 7 questions aimed at understanding participants' attitudes toward investing and their comfort with financial risks.
- **Financial Well-being and Life Goals:** 5 questions exploring how participants perceive their financial stability and long-term financial aspirations.
- **Ethical and Social Considerations:** 3 questions related to the ethical dimensions of financial decisions, including participants' views on socially responsible investing.
- **Expectations and Needs for Financial Education:** 8 questions focused on participants' views regarding the content and structure of financial literacy programs.
- **Reflections and Summary:** 2 final questions asked participants to reflect on their overall financial experiences and to summarize their expectations regarding financial education and planning.

2.4 Survey Administration

The questionnaire was distributed electronically via Google Forms, which provided ease of access for the participants. Each participant received a detailed email briefing on the objectives and purpose of the study prior to completing the questionnaire. The completion time for the survey ranged from 60 to 75 minutes, allowing respondents ample time to reflect on each question and provide detailed answers.

2.5 Data Analysis

The responses were analyzed using thematic analysis, a method commonly used in qualitative research to identify recurring patterns and themes within the data. Given the exploratory nature of the study, particular attention was given to identifying common financial attitudes, challenges, and educational needs among the participants. The analysis focused on understanding how participants' experiences and attitudes towards finance influenced their financial behaviors and how these behaviors could be addressed through targeted financial education.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

All participants were informed that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any point during the study. They were assured that their responses would remain confidential and that no personal identifying information would be used in the reporting of the results. The study adhered to standard ethical guidelines for qualitative research involving human subjects.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 *Financial Attitudes*

The data revealed that the financial attitudes of the respondents were predominantly shaped by early life experiences with money and family financial practices. A significant theme identified was financial conservatism, with 5 respondents indicating that their early experiences instilled in them a strong desire to save and manage their finances cautiously. For example, one respondent stated, "I need to have a safe amount of money stored away," reflecting an approach shaped by an ingrained sense of caution. The theme of calculated decision-making emerged as another important aspect, with 3 respondents stating that they meticulously planned their spending and saving decisions as a result of family habits or early financial lessons.

Frugality and prudence were also prevalent themes, with 4 respondents expressing a strong preference for saving over spending. One respondent said, "I developed a feeling of needing to save money at the same time," highlighting the tension between spending and saving, which was echoed by others who mentioned their upbringing emphasized disciplined financial behavior. Finally, confidence and discipline were significant, with 3 respondents indicating that they had developed a strong sense of control over their finances, attributing this to the discipline instilled in them by their early exposure to financial management.

3.2 *Financial Literacy and Education*

The analysis revealed a substantial gap in formal financial education, as 5 respondents indicated that they had not received any structured instruction on personal finance. This lack of formal education has forced many respondents to rely on self-taught learning (4 respondents), highlighting the importance of personal experience in filling this knowledge gap. However, the missed opportunities (3 respondents) in formal education are evident in the respondents' recognition that their ability to navigate real-world financial challenges was limited without formal guidance.

In terms of key financial literacy areas, 4 respondents identified budgeting, saving, and investment as crucial topics that should be taught to their peers. One respondent stated, "Budgeting and saving are essential for everyone in our age group," emphasizing the practical need for these skills. When discussing how financial literacy programs should be structured, 3 respondents mentioned that the content should be practical and relevant, focusing on real-world applications like scam detection and understanding loans.

Finally, the vast majority of respondents (5 out of 6) supported making financial education mandatory in academic curricula, with one respondent commenting that financial education is "just as important as mathematics." This consensus suggests a strong belief that formal education should address the financial needs of young adults, equipping them with essential life skills.

3.2.1 *Preference for Immersive Financial Education*

A notable finding was the preference for immersive learning methods. Four respondents expressed a desire for more engaging, interactive learning experiences. Two respondents specifically preferred game-based learning, citing its ability to provide hands-on, engaging learning experiences. Another respondent highlighted VR-based learning, describing it as a "fun approach" that could make complex financial concepts easier to understand. This preference for immersive methods reflects a broader trend in education toward interactive, technology-driven solutions for learning.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study are consistent with existing literature on financial attitudes and education. Previous research has shown that early life experiences significantly shape financial behaviors in adulthood. For example, Shim et al. (2009) found that parents and early financial experiences play a crucial role in developing financial behaviors in young adults. In our study, respondents who had early exposure to money management through pocket money, family financial habits, or informal lessons developed a cautious, conservative attitude toward finance. This reflects the broader notion that financial socialization begins at home and continues throughout adolescence, influencing adult financial decision-making (Gudmunson & Danes, 2011).

The findings also align with the theory of financial self-efficacy, which emphasizes the role of early experiences in developing an individual's confidence in managing financial resources (Lown, 2011). In this study, respondents who developed disciplined financial habits reported greater confidence and control over their financial decision-making. These findings suggest that individuals who are exposed to financial management at an early age are more likely to feel competent in handling their finances, confirming prior research on the importance of early financial socialization.

In terms of financial education, the lack of formal instruction noted by respondents echoes broader concerns in the literature about the inadequacy of financial education in traditional schooling (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). Many studies have highlighted the gap in personal finance instruction, noting that schools often fail to equip students with the skills they need to navigate complex financial decisions in adulthood (Mandell, 2008). Our respondents emphasized the importance of practical topics like budgeting, saving, and investment, which are commonly cited in the literature as foundational aspects of financial literacy (OECD, 2015).

Moreover, the strong preference for immersive learning methods, such as game-based learning and VR experiences, is consistent with recent trends in financial education research. Immersive methods have been found to enhance engagement and retention in financial literacy programs, particularly among younger learners who respond better to interactive, technology-based formats (Friedrich, 2020). For instance, game-based learning has been shown to improve financial knowledge and behavior by making learning more accessible and enjoyable (Xu & Zia, 2012). The respondents' desire for immersive formats suggests that traditional, lecture-based financial education may not be as effective in engaging younger audiences, who are increasingly accustomed to digital, interactive learning environments.

Lastly, the respondents' support for making financial education mandatory aligns with global initiatives to integrate financial literacy into national curricula. Countries such as Australia and New Zealand have made significant strides in embedding financial education within their schooling systems, recognizing the need to prepare students for real-world financial challenges (OECD, 2015). The respondents in this study reflected similar views, advocating for financial literacy to be considered a fundamental component of education alongside traditional subjects like mathematics.

5. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the critical role of early life experiences in shaping financial attitudes and the substantial gap in formal financial education that many young adults face. The findings underscore the importance of financial socialization during childhood, with respondents demonstrating conservative, disciplined financial attitudes that stem from their early exposure to money management.

However, the lack of formal financial education poses a challenge, as many respondents indicated they have had to rely on self-directed learning to fill this gap.

The strong preference for practical, real-world financial literacy programs further supports the need for education systems to prioritize personal finance instruction. Respondents favored immersive, engaging methods like game-based learning and VR experiences, indicating that traditional classroom formats may be insufficient in meeting the needs of younger learners. This reflects broader trends in education, where interactive, technology-driven approaches have been shown to enhance engagement and knowledge retention.

Given these findings, it is crucial that educational institutions and policymakers consider making financial education a mandatory part of academic curricula. Doing so would not only bridge the knowledge gap but also equip young adults with the skills they need to navigate increasingly complex financial environments. Future research should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of immersive financial education programs and exploring how early financial socialization can be integrated into formal education systems to foster lifelong financial competence.

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